

ANALYTICAL STUDIES OF PHOTOCHEMICALLY DEGRADED JUTE. PART II

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The photochemical changes of jute fibre do not appear to be influenced by the uronic acid constituent. The acidic and reducing types of substances, which are generated in the fibre during irradiation, are derived mainly from the lignin component. The acidic reaction products or the constituent uronic acid have no hydrolytic influence on the fibre, indicating that in the photochemical degradation of jute, acidic components do not contribute to the accelerated degradation.

In a previous communication (Macmillan and Bhattacharjee, *this Journal*, 1955, 32, 731), results of analytical studies of the carbohydrate fractions, isolated from jute fibre exposed to light for increasing lengths of time, have been reported. Because of the severity of treatments involved in the isolation processes, which are likely to further modify the degraded components, the results of the observation provide only a rough indication of the extent of degradation suffered by the components and do not supply sufficient information regarding the photochemical changes of the fibre, which may help to elucidate the mechanism of the enhanced degradation of jute effected by exposure to light.

The reactions involved in the photochemical degradation of pure cellulose itself is highly complicated, and not yet precisely understood. In jute it is likely to be still more complicated due to the presence of a considerable portion of non-cellulosic components comprising mainly hemicellulose and lignin, which may accelerate the degradation of the fibre through the influence of the constituent groupings such as carboxyl, acetyl and others, or through various types of reaction products formed during irradiation. Of the constituent groupings, the uronic carboxyl groups of the hemicelluloses appear to be the probable sources of hydrolytic degradation. The major portion of this acid group, however, exists in combination (Sarkar, Chatterjee and Mazumdar, *J. Text. Inst.*, 1947, 38, T318), partly in the form of an ester linkage with lignin and partly in the form of salts with cations: the rest representing about one-eighth of the total and amounting to about 3 m. e./100 g. of jute, exists as free acid. It is not yet known whether this amount of the free uronic acid has any additional degradative effect on the fibre under the conditions of photochemical reaction. The knowledge of the various types of reaction products generated during irradiation of jute and their influence on fibre properties is also limited. Although acidic bodies have been known to be formed, the components from which they are derived have not been precisely explained. Ludtke (*Biochem. Z.*, 1936, 284, 90) remarked that increase in acidity and disintegration of jute fibre originated from the constituents other than the cellulose. Callow and Speakman (*J. Soc. Dyers & Col.*, 1949, 66, 758) expressed the view that the acidity in jute exposed to light arose from degradation of the polyuronide hemicelluloses and lignin. No mention has been made as to whether the constituent

acetyl groups are involved in the generation of acids, although the authors have shown that free acetic acid is liberated from the acetyl groups of acetylated jute on irradiation. It is, however, not known whether the acidic products, which are generated during irradiation of jute, have any additional degradative effect on the fibre. Barker (*J. Text. Inst.*, 1939, 30, P289) when discussing the degradation of jute fibre under certain storage conditions considered it unlikely that the amount of natural acidity generated in jute fibre during storage would serve of its own to cause hydrolysis of the cellulose. The increase in acidity should be regarded more a symptom rather than a cause of degradation of the fibre. It was also pointed out that although the acids resulting from oxidation of the lignin "might not be formed in sufficient quantity to have any measurable effect on the cellulose, yet oxidation and/or hydrolysis of cellulose might be introduced simply because this component is in intimate contact with the oxygen acceptor". Besides acidic bodies, a volatile peroxide, presumably hydrogen peroxide, has recently been shown to be produced from the lignin fraction of the fibre during irradiation (Macmillan and Bhattacharjee, *J. Text. Inst.*, 1954, 45, T700). The mode of formation of this peroxide is similar to that observed with a number of photo-sensitive dyes or inorganic oxides which produce hydrogen peroxide under the influence of light through a sensitising mechanism (Egerton, *ibid.*, 1948, 39, T305). The accelerating influence of this peroxide is well known in the photochemical degradation of pure cellulosic fibres and it has been demonstrated that a similar accelerated degradation also takes place with the lignin in jute. With the latter, however, the matter is complicated by the presence of different acidic components in the system, and therefore it is difficult to say whether the enhanced degradation of jute is due to the peroxide alone or to a combined effect of the peroxide and the acids present in the fibre.

In order to throw more light on the causes of enhanced degradation of jute, it is desirable that further knowledge regarding the influence of the various factors involved, especially of the acidic components, should be made available. With this end in view, experiments were designed to obtain additional information on the nature of the photochemical changes of the fibre containing different amounts of free uronic acid liberated. The results of the observations are recorded in this part of the series. The nature of the chemical changes of the isolated fibre components on irradiation, and the influence of the free uronic acid and acidic degradation products on the tensile strength of the fibre under the conditions of photochemical reactions have also been investigated and the results described.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Jute yarn of 8-lb. grist, representing normal mill production, and a good quality tossa jute were used in the investigations. After the preliminary procedure of deoiling and water-washing, appropriate portions of materials were subjected to further treatments to liberate the uronic acid groups, and also to isolate the different components of the fibre, the yarn and the fibre samples being used respectively for these purposes. A treatment with $N/10$ -HCl for 1 hour at room temperature with a liquor ratio 50:1 was employed to remove the cations, and with 2% NaOH solution at room temperature

for 4 hours using a 50:1 liquor ratio, followed by a similar acid treatment to liberate the total amount of uronic acid present in the fibre. The samples thus prepared will be referred to as "cation-free" and "hydrolysed" jute respectively, and the untreated one as "deoiled" jute. The different fractions isolated from the fibre consisted of holocellulose, the Norman and Jenkins cellulose and lignin, the fractions being isolated by employing sodium chlorite (Chattopadhyay and Sarkar, *Proc. Nat. Inst. Sci. India*, 1946, 12, 23), sodium hypochlorite (Dorée, "The Methods of Cellulose Chemistry", 1947, p. 358) and 72% sulphuric acid (Sen Gupta and Callow, *J. Text. Inst.*, 1949, 40, T650) respectively.

Exposure to Light.—A carbon arc fadeometer of FDA-R (Atlas Electric Devices Co.) type with wet wicks was used for light exposure. The yarn was wound round a black cardboard (7" × 4") with portions placed on the board parallel to one another without overlapping. The board was then mounted on a specimen holder and exposed to light on one side only. Several mounted boards prepared from the three sets of yarn samples were thus exposed under identical conditions and, after a regular interval of 20 hours, two from each set were withdrawn for test purposes, the rest being allowed further exposure, the period of exposure being extended to a maximum of 60 hours.

In the case of the isolated fractions, since the Norman and Jenkins cellulose and lignin were obtained in powder form, the other samples, namely, holocellulose and the deoiled fibre, which was also included in the group for a comparative study, were reduced to powder in a Christy-Norris high speed mill with a view to making the conditions of exposure in the different samples similar as far as practicable. To expose the samples, the powdered material (1 g.) was spread uniformly over an area of 7 × 9 cm² on a clean glass plate (1.5 mm thick), covered and clamped with a similar glass plate, the assembly being mounted on a specimen holder and exposed for 30 hours on each side. The different samples were thus exposed simultaneously for a total period of 60 hours.

Analysis and Testing.—The exposed portions of the yarns were collected, cut into small lengths, thoroughly mixed and subjected to chemical analyses according to the procedures already described (*loc. cit.*, 1955). The powdered samples were also well mixed after collection from the glass plates prior to analysis.

The tensile strength of the yarn samples, conditioned at 65% R. H. and 72°F, was determined in a Goodbrand single thread tester, with 6-inch grip length, a mean of 100 tests being recorded for each sample.

DISCUSSION

The results summarised in Table I show that rise in water-solubility, noted with progressive exposure, is not affected by the increase in the free uronic acid groups in the fibre. Loss in weight appears to be slightly higher in the hydrolysed sample, probably due to dissolution of a higher amount of hemicelluloses, and this trend is maintained even after exposure for increasing lengths of time. But the increase in solubility recorded after exposure to light in all the corresponding samples, especially after 60 hours of exposure, is of the same order, the figures being 4.6%, 4.9% and 4.7% in the deoiled, cation-free and hydrolysed samples respectively.

TABLE I

Effect of light on water solubility and p_H of aqueous extract of jute.

Exposed for.	D e o i l e d.		C a t i o n - f r e e.		H y d r o l y s e d.	
	Water solubility. *	p_H of extract.	Water solubility. *	p_H of extract.	Water solubility. *	p_H of extract.
Nil	1.7%	6.0	1.8%	6.0	2.6%	5.6
20 hrs.	3.2	4.4	3.7	3.7	5.4	3.8
40	5.0	4.1	5.6	3.5	6.8	3.5
60	6.3	4.0	6.7	3.5	7.3	3.5

* Expressed in terms of loss in weight suffered on extraction with water under reflux for 30 minutes with a liquor ratio of 50:1.

The p_H of the aqueous extracts of the exposed samples is lowered gradually with increase in the period of exposure, but the level is much lower in the cation-free or hydrolysed sample than in the corresponding deoiled sample. That this variation is due to the influence of cations present in the deoiled fibre and not to the increased amounts of acidic products, generated in the other samples, is shown from the results summarised in Table II.

TABLE II

Effect of light on the acid value † of deoiled, cation-free and hydrolysed jute.

Exposed for.	D e o i l e d.		C a t i o n - f r e e.		H y d r o l y s e d.	
	Exposed.	Exposed and extracted. *	Exposed.	Exposed and extracted. *	Exposed.	Exposed and extracted. *
Nil	2.5	2.9	12.3	10.9	24.3	19.3
20 hrs.	6.8	7.3	16.8	11.5	25.5	15.8
40	10.3	8.8	20.3	12.5	26.2	15.4
60	12.3	9.6	22.3	12.9	26.6	15.3

† The figures represent acid values in milliequivalents per 100 g. of the oven-dried material.

* Figures expressed on the corresponding exposed samples.

The analytical figures show (Table II) that before water-extraction, the rise in acid value in the deoiled and cation-free samples exposed for identical periods of time is practically the same in both cases, the figures after 60 hours being 9.8 (12.3-2.5) and 10.0 (22.3-12.3) respectively. The corresponding figure of the hydrolysed sample is much less, being only 2.3 (26.6-24.3), probably due to partial removal of the acid-forming components during the alkaline pretreatment, a reference to which will be made later.

From the results it is evident that, for the same period of exposure, the amount of acid generated in the cation-free or the hydrolysed sample is not higher than that produced in the deoiled fibre.

The figures of acid values of the extracted samples show that acidity in the deoiled and cation-free jute increases with progressive exposure, the rise in the former being

markedly higher than in the latter. In the hydrolysed sample, on the other hand, a decrease in acid value is recorded. A comparison of the acid values of the exposed cation-free samples with the corresponding values noted after water-extraction indicates that the major portion of the generated acidic products is soluble in water and is removed by the treatment, a small fraction being left on the fibre which accounts for the slight increase in acidity of the extracted samples. While extraction of water-soluble products is simple in the cation-free fibre, it is rendered complicated in the deoiled fibre by the constituent cations which are provided with conditions favourable for side reaction. During the process of extraction, an equilibrium is likely to be set up in the system due to ion-exchange reactions between the hydrogen ions, derived from the extracted acids, and the cations present in the fibre, resulting in an apparent decrease in acidity of the extract with a corresponding liberation of the uronic acid groups in the fibre. This is probably the reason why the p_n values of the extracts of the exposed deoiled fibre are higher than the corresponding values noted in the cation-free fibre (Table I), and the rise in acidity of the extracted deoiled samples is higher than the corresponding values obtained in the cation-free jute (Table II). In the hydrolysed sample, the decrease in acidity of the extracted samples with progressive exposure probably arises from the dissolution of a portion of the constituent uronic acid along with the photo-degradation products in water. The possibility of dissolution of portions of the polyuronides in the deoiled and cation-free fibres also cannot be altogether excluded. The acid values of the extracted samples (Table II) therefore represent the resultant effects produced by the acidic degradation products and portions of the free uronic acid, which resist water extraction. A detailed study of the different components of jute, which are rendered water-soluble by photochemical reaction under the above conditions, is in progress and the results will be communicated later.

Changes in copper number of the samples are summarised in Table III. Gradual rise in copper number with progressive exposure is noted in all the samples, the rate of change being slightly higher in the cation-free jute. After extraction with water, the corresponding values are slightly reduced and the extent of this reduction is of the same order in the different sets of samples exposed for the same length of time.

TABLE III

Effect of light on the copper number of deoiled, cation-free and hydrolysed jute.

Exposed for.	D e o i l e d.		C a t i o n - f r e e.		H y d r o l y s e d.	
	Exposed.	Exposed and extracted. *	Exposed.	Exposed and extracted. *	Exposed.	Exposed and extracted.
Nil	2.1	2.1	2.1	2.2	2.2	1.6
20 hrs.	5.0	3.2	5.7	3.7	5.4	3.1
40	5.8	3.5	7.9	5.0	5.9	3.6
60	6.8	4.0	8.7	6.2	7.1	4.6

* The values expressed on corresponding exposed samples.

In order to ascertain whether the acidic or reducing types of degradation products are derived from lignin or the carbohydrate components, investigations have been carried out by exposing the isolated components, the analytical figures having been compared with those of the deoiled fibre exposed under identical conditions. As it was decided to expose the samples under the cover of glass plates, it was considered necessary to have some indication of the screening effect of the glass plate on the rate of the photochemical reaction by preliminary observations. For this purpose, solubility in 1% NaOH solution under reflux, which provided a better indication than water-solubility of the extent of degradation (*loc. cit.*), was determined on the deoiled yarn sample exposed in the usual manner and also under the cover of similar glass plates for 15 and 30 hours. When exposed as usual, the alkali-solubility was raised from 14.2 to 19.9 after 15 hours and to 23.6 after 30 hours, the corresponding values under the cover of glass being 19.3 and 22.6 respectively. The figures indicate that the glass plate has no appreciable effect on the reaction rate. The extent of yellowing, examined visually, also appeared to be of the same order in the samples exposed with or without the glass cover for the same length of time.

The analytical figures of the isolated components, summarised in Table IV, show that the rise in acid value and copper number of the Norman and Jenkins cellulose, holocellulose and jute, noted after 60 hours of exposure, increases with the lignin content of the materials, but in the isolated lignin the changes are less marked than in jute. The discrepancy is probably due to variation in the conditions of exposure of the lignin in the two cases. Although the extent of yellowing, resulting from light exposure, was more marked in the isolated lignin than in jute, it was observed that after a thorough mixing, preparatory to analysis, the lignin sample appeared to be far less affected in colour than the jute, indicating that reaction in the former was more confined to a thin superficial layer. Slight yellowing was also exhibited by the holocellulose, but the colour of the Norman and Jenkins cellulose remained practically unchanged.

TABLE IV

Effect of light on acid value and copper number of jute and isolated fibre components.

Time of exposure = 60 hours.

Samples.	Lignin content.	A c i d v a l u e *.			C o p p e r n u m b e r.		
		Original.	Exposed.	Increase.	Original.	Exposed.	Increase.
N.J. cellulose	0.15%	5.6	7.1	1.5	1.52	2.53	1.01
Holocellulose	1.30	8.9	14.0	5.1	0.37	2.78	2.41
Jute	13.60	2.4	18.4	16.0	1.46	10.10	8.64
Lignin	...	19.0	31.0	12.0	20.90	25.30	4.40

* m.e./100 g. of the oven-dry material.

The results of the observation suggest that lignin plays the major role in contributing to the rise in acid value and copper number of jute noted after light exposure.

In this connection it should be pointed out that the rise in acid value of jute on exposure is considerably decreased if the material is previously treated with an alkali (hydrolysed jute, Table II), although the treatment removes only a small portion of the lignin, amounting to 10% of the total present in the fibre. Acetyl groups were removed entirely by the treatment, and therefore, the possibility of the acetyl groups, when present in the fibre, contributing to the rise in acidity through formation of free acetic acid was examined. For this purpose, the acidity of the aqueous extract obtained from the cation-free jute exposed for 60 hours was determined on aliquot portions before and after distilling in steam for 1 hour, and it was noted that the acidity remained unaltered by the treatment, indicating the absence of any free acetic acid in the extract. The results lead to the conclusion that the acidity generated in jute on exposure does not arise from the acetyl groups but from the lignin, mainly from the portion which is soluble in alkali.

To investigate the influence of the free uronic acid groups on the tensile strength of jute under the conditions of photochemical degradation, tensile strength determinations were carried out on the deoiled, cation-free and hydrolysed yarn samples exposed for 60 hours in the fadeometer, the results being summarised in Table V. It will be noted that the loss in tensile strength tends to increase with increase in acidity of the fibre, but the rise is not proportional to the rise in acidity. The loss in tensile strength records a slight increase when the initial acidity of the fibre rises from 2.5 to 12.3, and is not further affected when the acidity rises to 24.3. It appears unlikely therefore that this rise in the loss in tensile strength is due to the increase in free acidity of the fibre; it may be due to other factors yet unknown.

TABLE V

Effect of light on the tensile strength of deoiled, cation-free and hydrolysed jute yarn.

Samples.	Acid value*.	Period of exposure = 60 hours.		Loss in tensile strength.
		Tensile strength (lbs.) before exposure.	Tensile strength (lbs.) after exposure.	
Deoiled	2.5	8.52 ± 0.167	3.69 ± 0.125	57%
Cation-free	12.3	8.35 ± 0.173	2.85 ± 0.079	66
Hydrolysed	24.3	8.43 ± 0.177	3.06 ± 0.072	64

* Figures taken from Table II.

To demonstrate whether the acidic reaction products generated during irradiation have any additional influence on the tensile strength of jute, cation-free yarn samples were treated with an aqueous extract of photo-degradation products and tested for any loss in tensile strength. The extract was prepared from cation-free yarns, exposed in the fadeometer for 60 hours, by refluxing for 30 minutes with distilled water with a liquor ratio of 10:1. After concentrating on a water-bath to one-fourth its volume, the extract was applied to the cation-free sample to be examined in a

proportion of 3 c.c. per g. of the material so that the entire amount of the extract was absorbed by the yarn during the treatment. The treated sample was dried in air and then divided into two halves, one being retained to serve as a control, the other being heated in an air-oven along with one untreated (cation-free), for 60 hours at 70° with a view to simulating conditions of time and temperature under which samples were exposed in the fadeometer. The amount of the acidic degradation products deposited is indicated by the rise in acid value noted in the control sample.

TABLE VI

Effect of acidic degradation products on the tensile strength of jute yarn.

Sample.	Acid value.	Tensile strength	
		before heating.	after heating.
1. Cation-free jute yarn	12.3	8.35 ± 0.173 lbs.	8.29 ± 0.131 lbs.
2. No. 1 treated with acidic degradation products	19.7	8.50 ± 0.159	8.38 ± 0.113

The figures shown in Table VI show that 7.4 (19.7-12.3) m. e. per 100 g. of acidic degradation products were deposited on the fibre as a result of treatment with the extract. The figure represents three fourths of the amount of the acids produced on the fibre (cation-free) *in situ* (22.3-12.3=10, Table II) when exposed for 60 hours in the fadeometer. On heating, the tensile strength of the untreated sample as well as of the treated remains unaffected, indicating that under the conditions of the experiment, the tensile strength of jute is not affected by the heat treatment and that the acidic photo-degradation products have no influence on the tensile strength of jute. The results suggest that, in photochemical degradation of jute, the acidity generated during irradiation has no hydrolytic influence on the fibre and therefore it appears that the main factor contributing to the enhancement of degradation of the fibre is the volatile peroxide which is generated from the lignin component during irradiation, as reported earlier.